

EFFICIENT STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE THROUGH COMPREHENSION IN LISTENING AND READING**Kostadinov O.D.**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878449>**Abstract**

Over the course of their life's experiences and particularly during their real study time, people pick up specific types of information. Learning a language requires more than just aptitude and hard work; it also must be done in a manner that is strictly consistent with human nature. Effective and efficient methods of learning a foreign language (both of which mean "capable of producing a result") are available. When something is effective, it achieves a result even if it requires more needless resources to do it, which is the difference between the two words' meanings. When something is efficient, it not only yields a result but does it quickly, easily, and with the least number of resources (materials, time, effort, etc.).

Keywords: Foreign word memorization; native language; listening, reading, speaking, writing in a foreign language; grammar, lexicology; the language of thought; passive language knowledge; active language knowledge; listening comprehension; reading comprehension; levels of language knowledge; fluency in a foreign language

*Research in Support of Modern Foreign Language Learning***1. Introduction**

The oldest intellectual ability that men have ever attained is language. The speaker's level of intellectual capacity can be determined by how well they understand it. Though it is theoretically feasible, we find it difficult to envision mind occurring without language. Apart from empirically validated instances of cognition existing independently of language, thought and language are two halves of the same coin. It is well known that a person sees the world through their five senses—the so-called perception systems—which include sight, hearing, smell, taste, and sensation. Humans are capable of perceiving using one or more perceptions in conjunction with other senses. Humans, for instance, understand language by vision and hearing (through reading). Humans can see what oral talks offer.

Since the need to master foreign languages is enormous and the process of learning is long and requires an expenditure of resources, foreign language teachers, as well as publishers of language literature, are in a constant process of improving foreign language education. Achieving this goal goes through the study of the human mind, how foreign language learners perceive and memorize, as well as the mechanism for teaching and efficiently learning new language units.

From a practical standpoint, language is a medium of communication, which means that people communicate with each other through language. Communication between people is the reason for the creation and development of languages. Human minds are the basis of communication between people. The human mind and the need for people to communicate with each other are the reasons for the emergence of language.

The current methodology for learning foreign languages is based on the natural way of learning them. In

addition, to speed up the learning process and shorten the time to reach the desired level of proficiency, the methodology includes a scholastic way of teaching, but is highly streamlined.

The natural way to learn a foreign language is by listening to live speech, accompanied by observing the environment and the facial expression of the speaker, i.e., the learners must "immerse themselves in the waters" of the foreign language which they study. It is especially important to note that in the initial stage of learning a foreign language, it is necessary to listen to foreign speech for a long time with a complexity corresponding to the level of the learner's knowledge. Subsequently, when the learner has already created his passive vocabulary of foreign words, in parallel with listening to foreign speech, the learner should go on with reading texts with a complexity corresponding to the level of the learner's knowledge, i.e., listening and reading texts with appropriate difficulty is the basis of natural acquisition of foreign languages. In parallel with listening to a speech and reading a text in the studied foreign language, learners must translate the vocabulary and do grammar exercises, but only of what they have repeatedly heard and memorized at a proper level. Gradual progress in the studied material, with consistent and multiple repetition of what learners have already learned, contributes to the permanent memorization of the learned language units. Learners of a foreign language should repeat what they have learned because each subsequent time of repetition improves the memorization of the language.

❖ **Definition for language:** *A system of signs for expression and exchange of human beings' thoughts by four language skills: listening, reading, speaking, and writing. Language gives people the ability to think and to communicate with each other.*

2. Human Intelligence, Human Memory, Methodology of Study, and Their Impact on Foreign Language Learning

Human Intelligence, Human Memory, and Methodology of Study are the three key factors for success in the learning of foreign languages.

❖ **Definition for Human Intelligence:** *The ability to think, to learn from experience, to solve problems, and to adapt to new situations is a variable more strongly related to successful educational, occupational, economic, and social outcomes than any other individual differences in human intellectual abilities.*

❖ **Definition for Human Memory:** *Human memory is the psychological process of acquiring, storing, retaining, and later retrieving information. There are three major processes involved in memory: encoding, storage, and retrieval.*

❖ **Definition for Methodology of Study:** *The definition of methodology of study is the most efficient way to obtain certain useful knowledge in order for the same to be used in human life.*

2.1. Memory as Categories, Phases, and Functions

According to the table below, human memory is characterized in terms of categories, phases, and functions.

Table 1

Model of Human Memory	
Categories, Phases and Functions of Human Memory	
Categories	Explicit memory
	Implicit memory
Phases	Sensory memory
	Short-term memory
	Long-term memory
Functions	Transition
	Repository
	Retrieve

For the development of effective educational approaches, it is crucial to comprehend the elements of the human memory model. One of the mental puzzles for which academics still lack a comprehensive solution is memory. The three-part model of memory was created by Richard Atkinson and Richard Shiffrin in 1968. The three primary parts of memory, according to the experts, are sensory memory, short-term memory (sometimes referred to as working memory), and long-term memory. Since then, it has evolved into one of the key theories used to explain how memory functions (Shiffrin et al. 2015).¹⁰

2.1.1. Categories of memory:

❖ Explicit memory

Explicit memory is when we try to recall something that has already happened, either on our own or with the help of another person. The knowledge we have acquired in the past, such as a remembrance of an experience, is known as explicit memory.

❖ Implicit memory

While explicit memory refers to things that we can consciously recall, implicit memory refers to knowledge that we cannot recall. *Implicit memory refers to the influence of experience on behavior, even if the individual is not aware of those influences.* (Waltinga, 2010)¹¹

2.1.2. Phases of Memory

Sensory, short-term, and long-term memory are the three stages of human memory. Since each of these three stages of memory is crucial for human intellect, it is imperative that students understand how human memory is divided. When developing foreign language learning approaches, all three of these phases must be taken into account from the perspective of acquiring a second (foreign) language.¹²

Phases of Memory: Sensory, Short-Term, and Long-Term Memory

¹⁰ Study Corgi (2021, February 8). Three-Component Model of Memory and Influences. Retrieved from <https://study-corgi.com/three-component-model-of-memory-and-influences/>

¹¹ Jennifer Waltinga, Charles Stanger, Introduction to Psychology – 1st Canadian Edition, 2010, p.363

¹² R. C. Atkinson and R. M. Shiffrin, Human Memory: a Proposed System and its control process, Stanford University, California, 1968, p.94,96,103

Fig.1: Memory duration¹³

2.1.2.1. Sensory memory: This kind of memory first arises during the brief, up to a few second, as a first stage of memorization. The sensory memory might be visual, aural, gustatory, olfactory, or tactile depending on the person's five senses. **Echoic memory**, a type of auditory sensory memory, and **iconic memory**, a type of visual sensory memory, are both crucial for language development.¹⁴

2.1.2.2. Short-term Memory: This sort of memory lasts only a few seconds to a few minutes and remembers a variety of pictures, words, numbers, facts, etc. The most recent information can quickly replace short-term memory, but it can also be easily replicated. Our short-term memory stores the information that receives our full attention. It is crucial to note that all words learned in a foreign language get into short-term

memory initially when learning the language. The brain retains this knowledge for a very brief period, usually less than a minute, but it cannot stay there permanently. **Working memory** is another name for short-term memory.

❖ **Short-term memory has three key aspects.**

- **Limited capacity:** It has limited capacity—it can store about seven items (letters, numbers, words, pictures, names) at a time.
- **Limited duration:** Storage is very fragile, and the information can be lost with distraction or the passage of time.
- **Encoding is primarily acoustic,** even translating visual information into sounds.¹⁵

Figure 2: Short-Term Memory Decay

¹³ Source: Introduction to Psychology – 1st Canadian Edition by Jennifer Wal inga, Charles Stango, 2010, p.366

¹⁴ Jennifer Wal inga, Charles Stanger, Introduction to Psychology – 1st Canadian Edition, 2010, p.367

¹⁵ McLeod S. A. (2009, December 14). Short-term memory, Simply Psychology. www.simplypsychology.org/short-term-memory.htm

On Fig.2—Decay of Short-term Memory, we can see when we store information in short-term memory and then it will be lost if we do not refresh it properly and enough.

Refreshing information to avoid losing it and then transferring it to long-term memory is one technique to stop knowledge from fading in short-term memory. Repetition of knowledge in the mind with the intention of retaining it in memory is known as maintenance rehearsal. To write it down or maybe store it in long-term memory, we must review the information whenever we want to remember it (such as names, phone numbers, and addresses of specific people).

2.1.2.3. Long-term Memory: This type of memory is long-lasting, and the information stored in it can be reproduced after a long period of time, such as years. The recovery of memory may take seconds until all the necessary parts of the brain activate.¹⁶¹⁷

❖ **Conclusion 1:** *In relation to learning a foreign language, we should say that auditory and visual memory are important, as well as other types of sensory memory that humans use to a small extent. The big task*

in learning a foreign language is for learners to perceive correctly studied material with their sensory memory, which makes it transfer to their short-term memory. The great difficulty in learning a foreign language is the transition of learned language units from short-term to long-term memory. It is also necessary for the reproduction of the language, which requires the rapid retrieval of the required language knowledge from long-term to short-term memory, also known as working memory. Fluency in a foreign language necessitates the storage of language knowledge in long-term memory.

❖ **Thesis 1:** *Human memory has limited capacity and duration. This is a problem that foreign language learners must be aware of and overcome. Foreign Language Learners should pay attention to the fact that human memory is able to receive and keep the latest information in short-term memory in the range of 5–9 items (words), before it goes to long-term memory and only after that can the learners proceed with the study of added information.*

3. Four types of skills for mastering a foreign language

The basic skills needed to master any foreign language are **listening, reading, speaking, and writing**. We can divide these four skills into two groups:

- **Listening and reading** to comprehend the concept presented in the foreign language. These two skills are necessary to understand the spoken and written language; they are the so-called input skills (**input info.**)¹⁸
- **Speaking and writing** a foreign language is our ability to present our or another person's thoughts in a foreign language. These two skills are necessary to express ourselves in the spoken and written language; they are the so-called output skills (**output info.**)¹⁹

4. Characteristics of the learning process for four languages

The characteristics of four language skills: listening, reading, speaking, and writing, listed in this order, are as follows:

- The degree of learning difficulty affects this ranking. The simplest skills to acquire are listening and understanding. Reading follows, followed by speaking and writing, in that order.
- It seems sense to think that before we can express ourselves in a language, we must first learn to understand it. The opposite is impossible.²⁰

¹⁶ Center for non-formal education, <https://www.abvgd-sofia.com/>

¹⁷ Article „What are the different types of memory?“, Medical News Today, <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/types-of-memory>

¹⁸ Article „The importance of input in the ELT classroom“, Cambridge University Press, <https://www.cambridge.org/elt/blog/2017/12/19/the-importance-of-input-in-the-elt-classroom/>

¹⁹ Article „Input and output in second language“, My English Pages, <https://www.myenglishpages.com/blog/input-and-output-in-second-language-acquisition/>

²⁰ Article „The Four Basic Language Skills“, Columbia Gorge, Community College, <https://www.cgcc.edu/literacy/resources/four-basic-language-skills>

The order of abilities required for language acquisition must always be followed when learning a foreign language. The alternative is a time and effort waster.

❖ **Conclusion 2:** *The basic conclusion on this point is that output foreign language knowledge always depends on input knowledge because we cannot express anything that we have not learned yet.*

❖ **Thesis 2:** *The important aspect of foreign language learning is the input process, which secures the necessary knowledge. This process supports the output process, which is necessary for refreshing knowledge. On the other hand, we can assume that during the input process, learners also refresh the knowledge they have already acquired. It is obvious that listening and reading texts at a suitable level are two constant activities, particularly important for maintaining language proficiency.*

5. Preparation of the state of mind when learning a foreign language

Foreign language acquisition is a voluntary intellectual activity that necessitates learners' undivided attention and mental focus. The mind gives one the ability to control their activities, although it can be difficult to manage their focus. Since the mind is not "**an automatic machine**," controlling attention can be done with restraint and the practice of paying close attention when others are speaking. We should also mention the learner's physical health, if he has had enough sleep, and the presence of any emotional problems as other crucial factors for the simple perception and learning of foreign languages. These factors go along with attention and concentration of the mind. The student can construct the ideal learning environment because the aforementioned components are under their control. Together with these

6. Ways to learn a second (foreign) language.

- A second (foreign) language can be learned naturally, through an organized form of learning with teacher participation, or through the traditional (scholastic) method, which involves an organized form of learning.

- Modern methods of learning a second (foreign) language have been developed because of extensive research in the field. According to linguistics, language acquisition is a personal endeavor, and different learners may benefit from various instructional approaches. On the other hand, psychology and human minds are similar. For this reason, science must do more in general to enhance learning foreign languages.

Thesis 3: *The author's opinion is that the best is this methodology, which has taken the best of the natural and the best of the traditional (scholastic) ways of learning a second (foreign) language, i.e., both ways of foreign language learning complement each other. In practice, it is best to find a balance between both ways.*

This balance is dynamic, and at different acquisition phases (levels), different ratios between the time of natural and scholastic language learning are preferable.

7. Foreign Language Learning by Listening Comprehension and Reading Comprehension

The current approach starts with learning the language through listening comprehension, followed by learning the vocabulary from the text through reading, translation, and learning the appropriate grammatical structures from the text. This approach is appropriate for those learning the language at level A1.²¹

The second main element of the current methodology is "**reading comprehension**"²² and it must be practiced in parallel with the continued learning of the language by "**listening comprehension**"²³, i.e., "listening comprehension" and "reading comprehension"²⁴, together with the parallel learning of the vocabulary from the text, by reading and learning the corresponding grammatical unit from the text. This methodology is suitable for beginners at language levels A1 and A2.

The third component of the process is the small-step approach to grammar acquisition, although each new grammar unit requires reviewing the prior material. If new and sophisticated forms are required, teachers must introduce them; in other words, grammar must be taught progressively and at various levels. Each grammar level contains the levels that came before it, but always emphasizes the level that is being studied most. This rule is applicable to all levels A1–C1, but students should obviously stress their areas of weakness.

The fourth component of the process is striking the right balance between learning new words and learning new grammar rules. Learners strengthen their weak areas of language proficiency in this way.

The fourth component is the ratios of time spent on hearing, reading, speaking, and writing, which are the fundamental abilities required for studying any foreign language, are the methodology's fifth and most important component. The learner can enhance one or more fundamental language skills in this fifth and most significant component of the foreign language learning methodology. For example, if the language is to be used professionally in some types of translation, this would be possible by emphasizing the relevant skills (interpretation from the foreign language; written translation from the foreign language; oral translation into the foreign language).

8. The process of learning unfamiliar words in a foreign language

Any foreign language acquisition process may be broken down into several stages and spans a period. Knowing this procedure will enable learners to select the approach that will help them learn each word most effectively. Memorization fails when foreign words are

²¹ Article "What is Listening Comprehension", All about Learning press, <https://blog.allaboutlearningpress.com/listening-comprehension/>

²² Article "Improve your students' Reading Comprehension," <https://readtheory.org/> (5 July 2022)

²³ Article "What is Listening Comprehension", All about Learning press, <https://blog.allaboutlearningpress.com/listening-comprehension>

²⁴ Research paper by Marcelo, Paul Bernal, using reading to teach English as a foreign language, MASKANA, Vol.11, No.2,18-26, <https://publicaciones.uca.edu.ec/ojs/index.php/maskana/article/view/3451>
doi: 10.18537/mskn.11.02.02

learned incorrectly. Ineffective learning causes students to spend time that may be spent learning more. Even with just a few readings and translations, learners can memorize specific words very rapidly, especially those in which they are personally interested, but this is not the true for many words. Learners frequently must translate the same words several times to memorize them. This is natural; however, it can be the result of incorrectly learning new terms.

Thesis 4: *Learners can perceive foreign words both audibly and visually by reading. The natural way of perceiving words is auditory, which suggests that this way of perceiving foreign words is also easier to memorize. Auditory perception has another indisputable advantage: together with the perception of words, learners can hear their correct pronunciation. But in no case, learners should neglect iconic memory. Reading and writing in learning a language is also particularly useful because it is a refreshment of memory.*

9. Stages of foreign language word learning

- The audible perception of unfamiliar foreign words. Unfamiliar foreign words can be heard in speeches or read in text.
- Learners must be able to clearly hear each word they hear in a speech. New words that are unknown should be accurately recognized before being properly uttered.
- When reading a text, readers should look up any unfamiliar words in a dictionary. Hearing the same word in an audio recording is beneficial as well. This feature is offered by some dictionaries, including Google Translate. Use dictionaries from recognized publishers is advised.²⁵
- With a suitable multistage learning process, unfamiliar foreign words can be learned.

9.1. First level of foreign language learning.

The first level includes the learning of foreign words without translation into the native language. Very often, learners hear unfamiliar words in combination with other lexical units (for example, prepositions). The current methodology requires that the new vocabulary should be the first presented to the learner through live speech, i.e., by audio recording or reading of the teaching material by the teacher. When the foreign language being taught is not the native language of the teacher, then it is better to use sound recordings of the so-called **native speakers**. Regardless of the source from which the unfamiliar word comes, learners should hear it repeatedly before moving on to the next stage of learning. The criterion for a sufficient sound presentation of new vocabulary is that the unknown words become recognizable to the learner, i.e., the word becomes as learned at the first level because the learners remember having previously heard that word. The correct pronunciation of words depends on their initial learning, which requires learners to hear the words very well and repeatedly.

The first meeting with the new and unfamiliar words is at the first phase of listening to the new vocabulary by **sensory** on to fig. 1-memory duration. In this phase of learning the new vocabulary, the learners' attention, their interest, and desire to hear and learn the unknown words are most important. The new vocabulary enters the **short-term memory** because of the focus. For its retention, it is necessary to hear the new foreign words several times before moving on to the next level. It is particularly important to note that, according to the theory, human memory can perceive up to seven units at once.

9.2. Second level of foreign language learning.

After learners hear one word repeatedly, teachers can then present it to the student and translate it into the learner's native language. It is especially important to use reputable dictionaries and to give students the basic meaning of the word and its meaning in the text they study. This process of repetition of the foreign word together with its meaning in the students' native language is useful because in this way, learners refresh sensory input, and it goes to the short-term memory. It is important to note that the capacity of short-term memory has a limit of seven items (letters, numbers, words, pictures, names...) at a time, i.e., any new teaching material should consider the physical capabilities of the human mind, and, from a theoretical point of view, it should not overload the learners. During an intensive study of the foreign language, in which in practice more than fifty unfamiliar words are heard per day, teachers must evenly distribute new unfamiliar words between the lessons of the day. Since the problem of losing information in short-term memory is increasing, learners can partially overcome it by constant repetition of the new vocabulary throughout all lessons during the day.

9.3 Foreign language learning at the third level.

At the end of the lesson per day, when the entire text of the material for the study has been translated and the student has written down the translations of all unknown words in the text accordingly, regardless of whether they are new unknown words or forgotten words from previous lessons, we can move on to a new multiple listening and reading of the text.

9.4 The fourth level of learning, in which all foreign word meanings are studied.

The study material should correspond to the planned vocabulary for study. At the end of the textbook, there should be a glossary with all the words used in the textbook, no matter whether they are from previous lessons and the textbook or not. All words must have equal repetition as far as possible. There is a need for continuity between the individual lessons in the textbooks. The fourth step in learning foreign words is learning all the meanings of the foreign words. There are languages, e.g., the English language, that include

²⁵ Article „Learning new words”, British Council, <https://learnenglishteens.britishcouncil.org/exams/grammar-vocabulary-exams/learning-new-words>

phrasal verbs and words with multiple meanings, suggesting that the fourth stage of word learning can take a long time.^{26,27}

10. Strategies for speaking fluently in a foreign language.

The fundamental objective of methods for foreign language learning is to attain the desired result (degree of language proficiency) in the most effective manner possible spending the least amount of time necessary to acquire the study material up to the desired level of foreign language competence. The phases of language acquisition must be completed by learners, regardless of their goals for their level of proficiency in a foreign language. The right training approach and careful organization of the training materials for each step of the training make it possible to reach the goal. Learners must progress through a series of stages to obtain the highest level possible. It is crucial in this instance that the intended learning material solely refers to the current.

❖ We can categorize the mastering of foreign languages into three degrees from a practical standpoint.

- Conversational level: calls for a vocabulary of 500–1000 words, mastery of the most important grammar rules, basic verb tenses, and the capacity to converse about everyday topics.

- Fluency level: being able to converse fluently on any topic as well as possessing a vocabulary of 2000–3000 words, verb tenses, and basic syntax are requirements for language proficiency. Language competence demands the ability to communicate clearly on any subject and the possession of a vocabulary of 2000–3000 words, verb tenses, and fundamental syntax.

- Expert level: the capacity to conduct translations on any subject and a vocabulary of at least 6000–8000 words are required for the expert level. In addition, one must be familiar with the complex verb tenses, other grammar rules, and the rest of the language to acquire a sophisticated speaking style.²⁸

11. Research

I am delighted to share with you my personal experience and experimental work on myself:

I spent over eight years learning English, but my progress was extremely slow at first. I had already mastered the basics of English grammar, but I was still feeling like a beginner. Then I could read and translate from English to my native language, but I could not speak. I also could not understand English speech. Once, by chance, I listened to an audio transmission by The Voice of America—Special English Program, which I liked very much. I continued to follow this radio program regularly. Very soon, I realized that I had improved my English very much. I also started to speak and have real dialogue with British people. I can now say that the Special English Program of VOA and later BBC – Learning English programs helped me too

much. After 8 years of scholastic study of English, I started to listen to these radio programs, and they helped me to start speaking English fluently and later to reach an advanced level.

My second foreign language is Russian. I have never had an interest in Russian, but because it was a mandatory subject in my secondary and high school, I had to follow the school lessons regularly. The results of my Russian were extremely poor, but later when I started my career, I had to speak Russian at my job. Also, I used to watch Russian TV for a long time and can now say that I understand very well. When I don't know a certain Russian word, I usually refer to the dictionary. Now I can say that my passive Russian knowledge is excellent. I understand Russian very well when I read and listen, but when I speak Russian, I still make grammar mistakes, which is not a big problem for me because I usually use Russian for fun.

My third foreign language is Greek. I had Greek lessons with a teacher for 18 months. My Greek teacher taught me the basics of Greek grammar. I heard someone say that my passive Greek vocabulary consisted of about 750 words, but my active vocabulary had less than 300–350 words. I visited Greece 3 years after my first Greek lesson, and then I had my first live conversation in Greek. In comparison to my English lessons, I can say that the vocabulary I studied during my Greek lessons was not extensive, but instead of learning new unfamiliar words, I used to repeat what I had already learned. Later, I decided to follow a TV series in Greek. At the beginning, it was difficult for me to understand what I was hearing, but after 2–3 months of regular watching of Greek series, I began to understand well. Fifteen years after my first Greek lesson, I began to watch Greek series on YouTube.com Channel- (Family Stories), and now I am happy to say that I have begun to speak Greek fluently as a result of my regular viewing of Greek series.

My fourth foreign language is Italian. I started to study Italian 35 years ago. During this time due to lack of any satisfactory progress in Italian, I decided to stop studying Italian 3 times, but later I had continued without any progress again. Four years ago, I remembered myself how I had done my progress in English and Greek. That is why I decided to do the same by following YouTube.com channels in Italian language. Now I am happy with my Italian language progress. I understand Italian very well and planning to make a trip to Bella Italia to speak with Italians in the Italian language.

Personally, for me the best way to learn a foreign language for beginners is by listening comprehension, supported by grammar lessons in parallel. On upper stage of foreign language learning it is recommended reading comprehension supported by translations into both languages. The advanced grammar study is important too. I recommend language learners first to hear

²⁶ Article “6 Tips for Learning New Words”, British Council, <https://www.britishcouncilfoundation.id/en/english/articles/new-words>

²⁷ Article „Seven steps to vocabulary learning“, British Council, <https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/article/seven-steps-vocabulary-learning>

²⁸ Article: How many words do you need to know to speak a language well? Progress Language Train Solution, <https://1to1progress.com/blog/2021/12/03/words-you-need-to-know-to-speak-a-language/>

more times any suitable foreign language audio type and only when they are sure that they have clearly heard the unfamiliar words more times, then they can check the dictionary for correct translation of the unfamiliar words. Students are going to understand the meaning of unknown words before they check their correct meaning in the dictionary.

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